

On the acceptability of parking policy: Replacing on-street parking with space for street life, cycling, and vegetation in central Copenhagen

Kostas Mouratidis^{a,*}, Hans Skov-Petersen^a, Trine Agervig Carstensen^a

^a Department of Geosciences and Natural Resource Management, University of Copenhagen, Denmark

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Public acceptance
Sustainable mobility
Walking and cycling
Parking policy
Urban transport planning

ABSTRACT

This study explores public acceptability of transforming on-street parking into space for street life, cycling, and vegetation, using a real-world intervention in the city center of Copenhagen as a case. Data were collected via a survey ($N = 3869$) with voluntary participants from the municipality's citizen panel and car users of the city center. The results suggest that a large majority of the citizen panel supported the imminent removal of on-street parking, and its replacement with space for street life, cycling, and vegetation. Acceptability is significantly influenced by parking behavior, car dependence, and car-related attitudes. Permanent or frequent users of on-street parking and individuals with high car dependence, preference for car-based transport, or intentions to increase car use are likely to express lower support. Acceptability is also formed by the place of residence. Despite being offered access to a nearby parking garage without additional cost, residents of the city center show lower support as they are the ones directly affected, whereas residents of nearby neighborhoods with possibly low car dependence and good access to the city center are more supportive. Travel satisfaction also plays a role, with lower satisfaction with traveling to the city center linked to reduced acceptability. Sociodemographic factors shape acceptability: older age, health issues or disabilities, living with children, and higher income relate to lower acceptability, whereas female gender and tertiary education are linked to higher acceptability. These findings shed light on behavioral, attitudinal, spatial, and sociodemographic factors that can help guide successful urban planning and transport policies.

1. Introduction

Reducing car dependence is considered an important step towards addressing environmental challenges such as the climate crisis, air pollution, and resource depletion as well as societal challenges such as traffic collisions and mobility inequalities (European Commission, 2019; Hoffmann, 2019; IPCC, 2023; Sheller, 2018). Car dependence is a pressing issue for cities and urban regions. It can be reduced through a combination of strategies including compact city policies, investment in public transport and active mobility, and measures to discourage car use (Mouratidis, 2025a). Key measures to discourage car use are regulating parking space and reducing parking supply (Litman, 2017; Mingardo et al., 2015), for example, by eliminating on-street parking and converting it to space that promotes livability and sustainable mobility (Baumgartner & Lanzendorf, 2025; Creutzig et al., 2020; Kirschner & Lanzendorf, 2020b; Mouratidis, 2021).

For future design and application of successful parking regulations, local authorities need to consider public support. Understanding the

acceptability of different parking regulations and the factors that shape it can support more informed decision-making. However, though the acceptability of transport policies such as road pricing have been widely studied (Milenković et al., 2019; Schuitema, Steg, & Forward, 2010; Sun et al., 2016; van Wee et al., 2023), there is limited evidence on the acceptability of on-street parking removal and its contributing factors. In light of the environmental and societal externalities of car use, there is an evident need to address this gap in knowledge.

This paper aims to provide insight into public acceptability of on-street parking removal when combined with freed-up space for street life, cycling, and vegetation as an incentive. The research question of the study is “What factors contribute to the acceptability of removing on-street parking and replacing it with space for street life, cycling, and vegetation?” We draw on the case of Copenhagen, where approximately 600 out of 1050 parking spots were about to be removed from the streets of the historic city center during July–December 2024 as part of the city's ongoing Urban and Traffic Plan (City of Copenhagen, 2022). The study relies on a survey conducted in June 2024 focusing on

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: km@ign.ku.dk (K. Mouratidis).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2026.106836>

Received 23 June 2025; Received in revised form 11 December 2025; Accepted 30 January 2026

Available online 18 February 2026

0264-2751/© 2026 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

acceptability of the policy and travel behavior just before the removal of the parking spots. We examine key factors for acceptability including: parking behavior (parking frequency and purpose), attitudes (car dependence and travel mode preference), intentions (car use intentions), satisfaction (travel satisfaction and walking satisfaction), sociodemographic factors (including age, gender, health status, income, and presence of children), and spatial factors (residential and workplace locations). Through this research, the study contributes new, context-sensitive knowledge on public support for parking policies and sustainable mobility transitions.

2. Theoretical background

The theoretical background is structured as follows. First, we explain the role of parking policy in shaping travel behavior and sustainability to provide the general background and motivation behind this study (Section 2.1). Next, we review studies on acceptability of urban and transport policies to provide a general understanding of the factors that shape policies relevant to the one our paper is focusing on (Section 2.2). Afterwards, we dig into previous studies that focus on the acceptability of parking policies, which is the main topic of the present study (Section 2.3). Then, we identify and present knowledge gaps that emerge from the review in Section 2.3 and explain how our study will address them (Section 2.4). Finally, we synthesize the theoretical basis for our empirical analysis based on the literature reviewed in Sections 2.2 and 2.3 (Section 2.5).

2.1. Parking policy and sustainable mobility

Reducing car dependence is a key component of sustainable mobility (Banister, 2008; Næss, 2020). Transitions to reduced car dependence include a series of push and pull strategies and interventions (Graham-Rowe et al., 2011; Leroutier & Quirion, 2023; Mouratidis, 2025a; Okraszewska et al., 2024; Scheepers et al., 2014; Schmaus et al., 2025; Semenescu et al., 2020). An important “push” strategy is to discourage car use through targeted interventions that restrict car traffic and parking (Mouratidis, 2025a). Parking policy and, in particular, parking regulations are key instruments of this strategy (Kuss & Nicholas, 2022; Santos et al., 2010).

Parking regulations include parking charges, parking restrictions for specific uses or types of vehicles, time regulations, as well as reducing parking supply (Burchell et al., 2019; Gillen, 1978; Kirschner & Lanzendorf, 2020a; Litman, 2017). These regulations are based on the fact that a generous parking supply is conducive to car use and car dependence (Litman, 2017; Shoup, 2021; Stefánsdóttir et al., 2024). Limiting free parking restricts and discourages car use thus reducing vehicle traffic, congestion, and air pollution, while improving livability in urban space and helping to enhance mobility through modes other than the private automobile (Mouratidis, 2025a).

Reducing the supply of available parking – either on- or off-street – is a key intervention to discourage car use that has been applied to several cities worldwide (Mingardo et al., 2015) and is currently part of several plans in cities of Europe (City Council of Seville, 2021; City of Amsterdam, 2013; City of Copenhagen, 2022; City of Paris, 2023; Oslo Municipality, 2019). Reducing parking supply is more prominent in city centers, neighborhood centers, and commercial streets. However, other types of parking regulations are often found in residential neighborhoods. Eliminating space for on-street parking naturally frees up space for other uses (Mouratidis, 2025a). Freed up space can be used to support other transport modes, by providing space for walking, spaces for bicycle infrastructure such as cycling lanes or bicycle parking, space for parking designated to shared mobility modes like shared cars, bicycles, and e-scooters, or space for public transport infrastructure. Moreover, space freed up by reducing on-street parking can accommodate new green spaces and foster urban life through the use of public spaces and outdoor sitting spaces of cafes and restaurants.

2.2. Acceptability of urban and transport policies

In the context of the present study, *acceptability* is defined as an attitudinal judgment of how good and fair a policy is perceived to be. Another relevant but not equal term (despite sometimes being used interchangeably in literature) is *acceptance*, which refers to the extent to which people comply with and support a policy in practice. The public acceptability of urban and transport policies depends on several factors including the type of policy, the level of deliberation and communication within the community, and contextual factors like culture and attitudes (Glavic et al., 2017; Kyriakidis et al., 2023; Moeinaddini & Habibian, 2023; Steg, 2003). Other factors that influence public acceptability are the perceived effectiveness of the policy, spatial factors, travel behavior and intentions, travel-related attitudes and perceptions, and sociodemographic characteristics (Lanzendorf et al., 2024; Lightner et al., 2025; Mehdizadeh et al., 2024; Milenković et al., 2019; Mouratidis & Næss, 2024; Tvinnereim et al., 2020).

There are several theoretical approaches to understanding acceptance and acceptability (Alexandre et al., 2018). A socio-psychologic approach relevant to transport policy is the theory of planned behavior (Ajzen, 2002). Based on relevant studies, perceived fairness and freedom associated with a specific transport policy influence the acceptability of the policy, while the residential built environment and environmental concern may influence attitudes and intentions related to travel (Mouratidis & Næss, 2024; Sun et al., 2016; Thøgersen et al., 2021). Spatial factors – including density, proximity, and transport infrastructure – on different spatial scales influence attitudes, intentions, and in turn travel behavior (Næss, 2025; Nielsen & Skov-Petersen, 2018). However, not only attitudes and intentions influence behavior as the theory of planned behavior suggests, but also behavior influences attitudes (Kroesen et al., 2017; van Wee et al., 2019). Travel behavior and parking behavior may influence attitudes towards travel and parking, thus influencing the acceptability of parking policies. The levels of car use or car dependence, the frequency of parking, and the type of parking used are likely to determine the acceptability of new parking regulations. Another factor that may influence travel-related attitudes is travel satisfaction (De Vos, 2019). The satisfaction or dissatisfaction with traveling to destinations or with using a specific travel mode may influence attitudes towards travel to these destinations and towards a specific travel mode. These attitudes may in turn influence behavior, but also the acceptability of policies aiming to change travel or parking experience.

Public support for urban and transport policies often increases after implementation (Börjesson et al., 2012; van Wee et al., 2023). There are various examples in cities worldwide where some citizens and stakeholders strongly opposed policies that would nowadays seem unthinkable to be reversed. This is because, after implementation, citizens may experience positive impacts which change their attitudes towards the implemented policy (Schuitema, Steg, & Forward, 2010). A notable intervention is pedestrianization, which typically includes elimination of on-street parking. Pedestrianization often faces strong opposition, but after being implemented support grows, and eventually pedestrian zones in many cases represent some of the most popular and attractive areas in cities. A relevant example is the opposition – mainly from shop owners – towards the pedestrian area of central Copenhagen (Strøget) at its establishment in 1962. However, not all urban and transport policies enjoy increased support after implementation, as there are examples of policies where support levels remained the same or even decreased after implementation (Kyriakidis et al., 2023; Tvinnereim et al., 2020).

Pull policy measures tend to be more acceptable than push measures, and measures that have a low personal cost tend to be more acceptable than those with a high personal cost (de Groot & Schuitema, 2012). Here, the term personal cost does not refer only to financial cost, but is defined to also include perceived inconvenience and personal burden, as in de Groot and Schuitema (2012), and adverse consequences in general (Mehdizadeh et al., 2024). Interventions restricting car use are push

measures with a high perceived personal cost for car users – since the car may offer well-being benefits to its users (Morris et al., 2020; Mouratidis, 2025b) – so they are often less popular than other measures. Push measures that regulate, discourage, or prohibit car use are less likely to be acceptable if they are not combined with pull measures such as investment in other transport modes or attractive outcomes such as improvements in livability (Gärling & Schuitema, 2007; Lanzendorf et al., 2024; Thaller et al., 2024).

2.3. Acceptability of parking policies

As with other urban and transport policies, the acceptability of parking policies is influenced by various factors. These factors may influence the perceived personal cost or more generally the perceived outcome expectations from the policy and thus contribute to the level of acceptability (Schuitema, Steg, & Rothengatter, 2010). First, the type of parking regulation largely determines the level of acceptability (Kirschner & Lanzendorf, 2020b). Moreover, replacing eliminated parking with other uses can influence the support for parking removal. In some cases, citizens are more likely to support the conversion of parking space into green space than into space to be used by other travel modes, for example shared mobility modes, according to Baumgartner and Lanzendorf (2025). Conversely, the conversion of parking into bike lanes can receive even higher public support, according to other studies (Goetting et al., 2025; Lanzendorf et al., 2024). The location of parking space to be regulated and the parking behavior of citizens also influence acceptability (Baumgartner & Lanzendorf, 2025). Future intentions regarding car use also play a role: citizens who intend to change their behavior towards car use reduction have higher acceptability of regulations that restrict car parking (Kirschner & Lanzendorf, 2020b).

2.4. Knowledge gaps

Based on this literature review, we identify significant gaps in knowledge. *First*, although there are several studies on the acceptability of transport policies such as road pricing, only a few studies have examined the acceptability of parking policies, and in particular on-street parking removal. Given the importance of limiting parking supply in the transition towards reduced car dependence and sustainable mobility (explained in section 2.1), it is critical to understand how citizens react to plans for on-street parking removal. As a result of this general gap, we lack evidence on how a series of factors – sociodemographic, spatial, satisfaction, attitudinal, and behavioral – shape the acceptability of on-street parking removal. *Second*, the few prior studies examining acceptability of concrete plans for on-street parking removal use surveys with residents of selected neighborhoods, and not of the city as a whole (Baumgartner & Lanzendorf, 2025; Kirschner & Lanzendorf, 2020b; Lanzendorf et al., 2024). Thus, despite providing important insights into selected neighborhood populations, it is not possible to identify factors that shape acceptability among the population of the city. Nor it is possible to compare the views of the “affected” local population with the population of the rest of the city. Therefore, generalization possibilities are more limited. *Third*, the few relevant existing studies come mostly, if not exclusively, from Germany, highlighting the need for studies from cases with other characteristics. This study provides new insights that shed light on these gaps in knowledge.

2.5. Basis for empirical analysis

The empirical analysis of the paper is based on the theoretical background presented in Sections 2.2 and 2.3. The analysis will examine factors that may contribute to the acceptability of transforming on-street parking into spaces for street life, cycling, and vegetation. Below, we summarize these factors and refer to literature that supports their inclusion in such an analysis. Since literature on transformation of on-street parking is limited as explained in Section 2.4, the literature

used to support the selection of contributing factors in the analysis also includes studies on the acceptability of other transport policies as well as broader studies on travel behavior and attitudes. Here is a summary of the identified factors:

- parking behavior (Baumgartner & Lanzendorf, 2025) or generally travel behavior (Kyriakidis et al., 2023; Lanzendorf et al., 2024; Lightner et al., 2025)
- attitudes towards travel (Kroesen et al., 2017; Tvinnereim et al., 2020; van Wee et al., 2019)
- intentions to reduce car use (Kirschner & Lanzendorf, 2020a; Lanzendorf et al., 2024)
- travel satisfaction (De Vos, 2019; Kyriakidis et al., 2023)
- car ownership (Kyriakidis et al., 2023; Lanzendorf et al., 2024)
- spatial factors (Baumgartner & Lanzendorf, 2025; Kyriakidis et al., 2023; Lanzendorf et al., 2024; Mehdizadeh et al., 2024; Milenković et al., 2019; Tvinnereim et al., 2020)
- sociodemographic factors (Kyriakidis et al., 2023; Lanzendorf et al., 2024; Lightner et al., 2025; Mehdizadeh et al., 2024; Milenković et al., 2019; Tvinnereim et al., 2020)

3. Methods

3.1. Urban space and traffic plan in Copenhagen

This study focuses on changes in parking policy in the city center of Copenhagen, the capital of Denmark. These changes are part of the Urban Space and Traffic Plan for the Medieval City (City of Copenhagen, 2022). The plan includes a series of urban and transport planning measures in the Medieval City of Copenhagen (Fig. 1), which is the historical center of the city (also referred to in the paper as “the city center” for simplicity). The Medieval City covers approximately 1.1 km² and has 9000 residents, while numerous residents of the metropolitan area use the area daily for work, study, shopping, recreation, or social services. The plan was developed after public deliberation, co-creation processes, and a pilot trial with subsequent evaluation through questionnaire surveys. The Urban Space and Traffic Plan proposed that “car parking and car traffic in the future should take up less space than today. Instead, space should be given in particular to pedestrians and cyclists, to places without commercial purposes, to vegetation between the district's historic buildings, and to more considerate bicycle parking, ensuring that the area's historical stories can emerge more clearly. At the same time, delivery of goods and other necessary logistics must continue to function, and residents who use a car must be able to park near their home.” (City of Copenhagen, 2022, p.7).

To achieve these goals the plan proposed to remove approximately 600 out of the existing 1050 spaces for on-street parking and gradually convert them to bicycle parking and space for walking, street life, and vegetation. Most of the parking spaces removed were designated spaces for residents of the city center district. These spaces were to be relocated to an underground parking garage at the fringe of the city center. Residents of the city center district who owned a car and had a residents' parking license (the cost of which depends on the characteristics of the vehicle) would be entitled to an access card enabling them to use the parking garage without any extra cost. The removal of 525 parking spaces was implemented during July–December 2024.

3.2. Data collection

The study draws on data collected through a survey conducted in June 2024, exactly before the new parking policy was implemented. The aim was to assess public acceptability of the policy as well as travel behavior, attitudes, and experiences before implementation and to follow up later on with a second wave of data collection after implementation. Data collection was part of the project ELABORATOR (project 101103772) funded by the Horizon Program of the European

Fig. 1. Left: Map of the historic center of Copenhagen (area size: approx. 1.1 km²). Right: Billboard on a street in Copenhagen informing citizens of new parking regulations. Translation from Danish: “New parking rules in the Medieval City”.

Commission. Prior to the survey, the project team obtained approval for processing of personal data in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation and the Danish Code of Conduct and Research Integrity.

The survey was developed by the authors in collaboration with the Traffic Department of the City of Copenhagen. It was finalized after first being pilot-tested and revised. It was developed as an online survey, available in both Danish and English, and was distributed using two methods. First, it was sent out to the citizen panel of the municipality. This is a body of approximately 20,000 citizens from the entire municipality of Copenhagen who voluntarily respond to surveys prepared by the municipality on topics related to the development of the city. The citizen panel includes adults of all ages and socioeconomic characteristics and is representative of the population of Copenhagen (<https://www.kk.dk/politik/faa-indflydelse/borgerpanelet>). The survey was sent to the panel through the municipality's digital post system. Second, the survey was carried out with citizens on the streets of the city center, targeting car drivers who park on the streets of the city center either because they live in the area or because they use the area. Since on-street parking in the city center – even before the intervention – is limited and few people drive in the city center, obtaining a sufficient number of responses from those who park on the streets of in the city center would not be possible via the citizen panel. Therefore, a street survey method was chosen to increase the representation of this group among the total sample. The street survey was carried out by a specialized company. To identify citizens who use on-street parking in the city center, the company's interviewers were stationed on streets with parking spaces and approached individuals observed driving into or out of these spaces. In addition, they recruited further participants by asking passing pedestrians whether they use on-street parking in the city center. Both drivers observed entering or leaving parking spaces and pedestrians who reported using on-street parking in the city center were invited to complete the survey. Those who answered the survey on the street used a tablet, while those who could not answer on the street were given a flyer that contained a quick response code (QR code) and a web link that redirected to the online survey.

The total sample size is $N = 3869$ respondents. Out of these respondents, 3567 come from the citizen panel, while 302 come from the street survey. The response rate for the citizen panel is approximately 18%, while for the street survey it cannot be estimated due to lack of data on the number of people asked to participate and the lack of relevant field notes. The survey's questions were not set to be mandatory to increase data accuracy and reliability and reduce dropout rates. The response option “I don't know/Do not wish to answer” was also added when relevant. As a result of these strategies, there are many missing responses in the dataset, and the sample size is reduced substantially in

analyses that contain multiple variables.

The study's survey approach suffers from some limitations. First, participation in the survey was voluntary, therefore only a part of the citizen panel participated, which might have resulted in non-response bias. Second, the absence of field notes for the street survey and the lack of a response rate do not allow us to evaluate non-response bias for this sub-sample. Third, when comparing the sample's sociodemographic composition to that of Copenhagen population (Table 1), we observe that while some sociodemographic characteristics of the sample match those of the population (gender, unemployment rate, households with children), other characteristics are overrepresented in the sample, as typical for surveys such as this one. The average age and income in the sample are both higher than the average in the population, while highly educated people are also overrepresented. These differences may lead to bias in the results of the study. To address this issue, we include a multivariable analysis that accounts for relevant sociodemographic variables.

3.3. Variable descriptions

The variables used in the study are presented in Table 2, while the survey questions are also presented in a questionnaire format in Appendix A. The question asked to obtain the dependent variable of the study “acceptability of removing on-street parking from city center” was an adaptation of wording used in the Urban and Traffic Plan (City of Copenhagen, 2022). The explanatory variables include sociodemographic factors, car access/ownership, travel satisfaction, mode preferences, future car use intentions, car dependence, purpose of on-street

Table 1

Sociodemographic characteristics of survey participants and the population of Copenhagen.

	Survey participants (N = 3869)	Population of Copenhagen ¹
	Mean	Mean
Age (for population with 18+ years)	54.56	42.06
Female	50%	51%
Tertiary education	78%	54%
Unemployed	2%	2%
Household size (number of people)	2.16	1.99
Household with children	24%	24%
Household income (gross annual, approximate)	700,000 DKK	623,000 DKK

¹ Source: own calculations based on latest data from StatBank of City of Copenhagen and Statista.

Table 2
Variable definitions.

	Question	Scale	Notes for variable
Acceptability of removing on-street parking from city center	In the Medieval City, Copenhagen Municipality wishes to create more space for walking and cycling, for sitting down on a bench, for local city life, and for more greenery between the old buildings. This initially requires that the cars in the streets take up less space than today. Therefore, there will be fewer parking spaces in the streets, where in turn more bicycle racks can be added and, in the long term, urban spaces will be better. What do you think about this?	Very negative (1) Very positive (7)	
Frequency of on-street parking in city center	How often do you park a car in the streets of the Medieval City?	6–7 days a week 5 days a week 2–4 days a week Once a week Sometimes per month Less than once a month Very rarely Never	
Purpose of on-street parking in city center	What is the main purpose of you parking a car in the streets of the Medieval City?	List of possible purposes	
Car dependence	Do you consider yourself dependent on the car?	No, Yes to some extent, Yes a lot	
Future car use intentions	In the next few years, do you intend to use a car...?	More than today, Less than today, Same as today	
Car is preferred mode	What is your favorite mode of travel?	List of travel modes	Car = 1, all other modes = 0
Travel to city center	How satisfied are you with traveling to the Medieval City?	Extremely dissatisfied (1) Extremely satisfied (7)	
Travel in the city in general	How satisfied are you with traveling within Copenhagen in general?		
Walking in city center	How satisfied are you with		

Table 2 (continued)

	Question	Scale	Notes for variable
Car always available	walking within the Medieval City? Do you own or have access to a private car? (not shared or commercial vehicle)	No, Yes sometimes, Yes always	Yes always = 1, else = 0
Age	Year of birth:	YYYY	Calculated in years based on year of birth
Female	Gender:	Female, Male, Other, Do not wish to answer	Female = 1, Male = 0, Other = 0
Tertiary education	What is your highest education?	List of education levels	Tertiary education considered medium or long-cycle higher education or above
Unemployed	What is your current professional or employment status?	List of employment situations	Unemployed = 1, else = 0
Lives with partner or spouse	Do you live with a spouse/partner?	No, Yes	Yes = 1, No = 0
Household with children	How many of the household members are under 18 years old?	0, 1, 2, 3, 4 or more	Households with children considered those with 1 or more members below 18 years old
Household income equiv.	What is the total annual income of your household from all sources (gross income before taxation)?	List of income classes	Midpoint of respondent's income class divided by the square root of the respondent's household size
Health issue or disability (yes a lot)	Are you hampered in your daily activities in any way by any longstanding illness, or disability, infirmity or mental health problem?	Yes a lot, Yes to some extent, No	Yes a lot = 1, else = 0

Notes: The questionnaire is presented in Appendix A. The answers “Do not know” or “Do not wish to answer” were considered missing answers.

parking in the city center, and frequency of on-street parking in the city center. Descriptive statistics of all explanatory variables are presented in Tables 3 and 4, while a descriptive chart of the dependent variable is presented in Section 4.1. The survey also asked participants to provide information about their residential and workplace locations (see Appendix A) which were used for the spatial analysis of public acceptability presented in section 4.5.

3.4. Analytical approach

To answer the main research question of the study, we employ quantitative and spatial data analysis methods. First, we use a cross-

Table 3
Descriptive statistics of explanatory variables (1/2).

	Min/Max	N	Mean	s.d.
<i>Travel mode preferences</i>				
Car is preferred mode	0/1	3660	0.17	0.38
<i>Travel satisfaction</i>				
Travel to city center	1/7	3506	5.21	1.60
Travel in the city in general	1/7	3617	5.08	1.56
Walking in city center	1/7	3565	5.49	1.38
<i>Car access/ownership</i>				
Car always available	0/1	3859	0.58	0.49
<i>Socio-demographics</i>				
Age	19/93	2823	54.56	15.00
Female	0/1	3568	0.50	0.50
Tertiary education	0/1	3603	0.78	0.41
Unemployed	0/1	3624	0.02	0.12
Lives with partner or spouse	0/1	3566	0.63	0.48
Household with children	0/1	3579	0.24	0.43
Household income equiv.	37796/ 2500000	3031	565639.06	322845.64
Health issue or disability (yes a lot)	0/1	3529	0.03	0.17

Table 4
Descriptive statistics of explanatory variables (2/2).

	N	Proportion
<i>Frequency of on-street parking in city center</i>		
6–7 days a week	120	4.1%
5 days a week	43	1.5%
2–4 days a week	92	3.1%
Once a week	92	3.1%
Sometimes per month	202	6.9%
Less than once a month	280	9.5%
Very rarely	701	23.9%
Never	1403	47.8%
<i>Purpose of on-street parking in city center</i>		
Other	188	6.7%
I never park	1333	47.5%
Public services	84	3.0%
Shopping	393	14.0%
Recreation	367	13.1%
Studies	4	0.1%
Work-related activity	185	6.6%
Work in city center	100	3.6%
Live in city center	153	5.5%
<i>Car dependence</i>		
Yes a lot	740	19.7%
Yes to some extent	1154	30.7%
No (or does not use a car)	1866	49.6%
<i>Future car use intentions</i>		
More than today	308	8.7%
Less than today	348	9.9%
Same as today	2866	81.4%

Note: The questions on frequency and purpose of on-street parking in the city center were asked only to those who answered “Yes” to the question on whether they ever use a car.

tabulation analysis to understand how the frequency of on-street parking in city center relates to the purpose of on-street parking in city center. Second, we use Kruskal–Wallis and Mann-Whitney U tests to compare the distributions of acceptability (acceptability of removing on-street parking from city center) with those of selected explanatory variables. Third, we employ multivariable modeling to examine how the explanatory variables together relate to acceptability. We chose the ordered logistic regression approach since acceptability is an ordinal variable. Finally, we geocoded the respondents’ residential and workplace addresses – obtained through the survey (see Appendix A) – and converted them to points in a geographic information system (GIS). We then used a GIS-based hot spot analysis to identify spatial clusters of high and low values of acceptability. This analysis used the Getis-Ord G_i^* statistic and a distance band of 1 km, and applied corrections for

multiple testing and spatial dependence using the False Discovery Rate (FDR) correction method.

4. Results

4.1. Acceptability of on-street parking removal

Fig. 2 shows percentages of each response option to the question on acceptability of the intervention. The results show that acceptability is high overall among the total sample but differs substantially between respondents from the citizen panel and the street survey. This indicates differences between the general population and those who use a car in the city center. These differences are examined in depth in Sections 4.2–4.4 that follow.

Most respondents from the citizen panel have a positive stance towards the intervention, while there is a much smaller but still considerable proportion that has a negative stance (Fig. 2). Approximately 73% of these respondents view the intervention as somewhat positive, positive, or very positive. Conversely, 20% view the intervention as somewhat negative, negative, or very negative, while 8% view it as neutral. The most frequent response is “very positive”, given by 44% of these respondents.

Respondents from the street survey report substantially more negative views towards the intervention (Fig. 2). Approximately 42% of these respondents view the intervention as somewhat positive, positive, or very positive, while 46% view it as somewhat negative, negative, or very negative, and 13% view it as neutral. The most frequent response is “very negative”, given by 19% of these respondents.

4.2. Use of on-street parking

Table 5 presents a cross-tabulation analysis of the frequency and the purpose of on-street parking in the city center. These questions were only asked to car users. The aim of this analysis is to provide an overview of the most common purposes for using on-street parking in the city center. This overview is useful when interpreting the analysis of factors that contribute to acceptability presented in the next sections. The analysis in Table 5 shows that those who live in the city center are those who use on-street parking more frequently. Among those who live and use on-street parking in the city center, 66.7% use it on a regular basis (6–7 days per week or permanently). Those who work and use on-street parking in the city center are the second most frequent users with 23% of them parking 5 days a week. Those who use on-street parking in the city center for other purposes use it more sporadically.

Next, we conducted Kruskal–Wallis tests to compare the distributions of acceptability of removing on-street parking from the city center with those of frequency and purpose of on-street parking. Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 show box plots from the analysis, while significance levels from pairwise comparisons are reported in Appendix B. Fig. 3 shows that the more one uses on-street parking the lower the acceptability of parking removal is. Those with the highest acceptability are those who never or very rarely park in the city center, while those with the lowest acceptability are those who park 5 days a week or 6–7 days a week. Fig. 4 shows that those who park and live in the city center tend to have lower acceptability of on-street parking removal than the other users of on-street parking. This is most likely due to the more frequent use of on-street parking by those who park and live in the city center compared to the more sporadic use by other users.

4.3. Car dependence and mode preference

The next part of the analysis compares the acceptability of on-street parking removal across different levels of car dependence and travel mode preferences, using Kruskal–Wallis and Mann-Whitney U tests respectively. Fig. 5 (left) shows that the more car dependent the respondent, the lower the acceptability of the intervention. Respondents

Fig. 2. Acceptability of removing on-street parking from the city center. N = 3637.

Table 5

Cross tabs of frequency of on-street parking in city center and purpose of on-street parking in city center.

Frequency of on-street parking in city center	Purpose of on-street parking in city center					I never park	Total
	Live in city center	Work in city center	Work-related activity	Shopping, recreation, studies, public services, and other			
Never	Count	2	1	2	59	1227	1291
	%	1.30%	1.00%	1.10%	5.69%	92.10%	46.00%
Very rarely	Count	23	17	40	522	91	693
	%	15.00%	17.00%	21.60%	50.39%	6.80%	24.70%
Less than once a month	Count	4	15	28	220	10	277
	%	2.60%	15.00%	15.10%	21.24%	0.80%	9.90%
Sometimes per month	Count	3	12	41	139	4	199
	%	2.00%	12.00%	22.20%	13.42%	0.30%	7.10%
Once a week	Count	7	8	26	51	0	92
	%	4.60%	8.00%	14.10%	4.92%	0.00%	3.30%
2-4 days a week	Count	6	13	37	36	0	92
	%	3.90%	13.00%	20.00%	3.47%	0.00%	3.30%
5 days a week	Count	6	23	10	4	0	43
	%	3.90%	23.00%	5.40%	0.39%	0.00%	1.50%
6-7 days a week	Count	102	11	1	5	0	119
	%	66.70%	11.00%	0.50%	0.48%	0.00%	4.20%
Total	Count	153	100	185	1036	1332	2806
	%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

who are not car dependent tend to have a very positive stance (median = 7) towards the intervention. Those who are somewhat car dependent tend to have a positive stance (median = 6), while those who are very car dependent tend to have a somewhat negative stance (median = 3). Fig. 5 (right) shows a significant difference between respondents who prefer the car and those who prefer other travel modes. Those who prefer the car as a travel mode tend to have a somewhat negative stance (median = 3) towards the intervention, while those who prefer other modes tend to have a positive stance (median = 6).

4.4. Model of acceptability of on-street parking removal

Next, we model the acceptability of on-street parking removal using

a multivariable approach. We developed ordered logistic regression models (Table 6) that examine how specific sets of explanatory variables are associated with acceptability. Model 1 includes variables on parking behavior, Model 2 includes variables on car-related attitudes, experiences, and car ownership, Model 3 includes sociodemographic variables, while Model 4 is the full model that includes all explanatory variables together.

Looking at the coefficients of determination in Table 6, Model 4 has the highest R-squared, as expected since it is the full model. A Nagelkerke R-squared of 0.459 indicates a relatively good fit for the full model. Model 3 has a low R-squared, suggesting that sociodemographic variables predict only a small proportion of total variation of the dependent variable. Model 1 has a modest R-squared, while Model 2 is

Fig. 3. Box plots of acceptability of removing on-street parking and frequency of on-street parking. Kruskal-Wallis test comparisons are reported in Appendix B.

Fig. 4. Box plots of acceptability of removing on-street parking and purpose of on-street parking. Kruskal-Wallis test comparisons are reported in Appendix B.

Fig. 5. Left: Box plot of acceptability of removing on-street parking and car dependence. Kruskal-Wallis test shows that all differences are statistically significant with $p < 0.001$. Right: Box plot of acceptability of removing on-street parking and travel mode preference. Mann-Whitney U test shows that differences are statistically significant with $p < 0.001$.

the model that has the second highest R-squared after the full model, suggesting that car dependence and car-related attitudes and experiences are the most important factors for acceptability, among the variables analyzed in the present study.

The results of Model 1 in Table 6 show that when frequency and purpose are modeled together, it is frequency that yields significant outcomes. Specifically, it is shown that more frequent use of on-street parking is associated with lower acceptability. Those who regularly

Table 6
Ordered logistic regression models of acceptability of removing on-street parking from the city center.

	Acceptability of removing on-street parking from city center			
	Model 1 Parking behavior	Model 2 Attitudes	Model 3 Socio-demographics	Model 4 Full model
<i>Frequency of on-street parking in city center</i>				
6–7 days a week	–2.866***			–1.595***
5 days a week	–2.483***			–0.433
2–4 days a week	–1.967***			–0.922*
Once a week	–2.153***			–0.961**
Sometimes per month	–1.645***			–0.961**
Less than once a month	–1.200***			–1.049***
Very rarely	–0.597***			–0.485*
Never (baseline)	0			0
<i>Purpose of on-street parking in city center</i>				
Other	–0.127			0.820*
I never park	0.145			0.802*
Public services	–0.353			0.734
Shopping	–0.160			0.908*
Recreation	–0.163			0.736*
Studies	0.428			–0.358
Work-related activity	–0.221			0.759*
Work in city center	0.008			0.423
Live in city center (baseline)	0			0
<i>Car dependence</i>				
Yes a lot		–1.655***		–1.307***
Yes to some extent		–0.923***		–0.746***
No (baseline)		0		0
<i>Future car use intentions</i>				
More than today		–0.173		–0.477**
Less than today		0.468***		0.493**
Same as today (baseline)		0		0
<i>Travel mode preferences</i>				
Car is preferred mode		–1.017***		–0.884***
<i>Travel satisfaction</i>				
Travel to city center		0.213***		0.178***
Travel in the city in general		0.275***		0.286***
Walking in city center		–0.220***		–0.229***
<i>Car access/ownership</i>				
Car always available		–0.615***		–0.482***
<i>Socio-demographic characteristics</i>				
Age			–0.022***	–0.015***
Female			0.213**	0.089
Tertiary education			0.821***	0.557***
Unemployed			–0.352	–0.439
Lives with partner or spouse			0.178*	0.613***
Household with children			–0.294**	–0.043
Household income equiv.			–0.000***	–0.000
Health issue or disability			–1.231***	–0.319
<i>Summary statistics</i>				
N	2661	3158	2274	1542
Nagelkerke R-squared	0.218	0.397	0.088	0.459

park (6–7 days a week or permanently) in the streets of the city center tend to have lower acceptability of on-street parking removal. The purpose of on-street parking is not significantly related to acceptability, when parking frequency is accounted for.

The results of Model 2 in Table 6 show that car dependence is associated with lower acceptability of on-street parking removal. Those who are very car dependent tend to have lower acceptability than those who are somewhat car dependent and those who are not car dependent. Car use intentions are also found to be associated with acceptability. Respondents who intend to use the car less frequently in the future tend to have higher acceptability than those who intend to maintain the same frequency and those who intend to use it more frequently. Travel mode preferences are also linked with acceptability. Those who prefer the car as a travel mode tend to have lower acceptability of on-street parking removal. Car ownership is also associated with acceptability. Those who always have access to a car in their household tend to be less supportive towards the removal of on-street parking. Moreover, travel satisfaction is also related to acceptability. Respondents who are satisfied with traveling to the city center and with traveling in the city in general have

higher acceptability of on-street parking removal. Although general travel satisfaction is positively associated with acceptability, satisfaction with walking is negatively associated with acceptability. Those who are satisfied with walking in the city center tend to accept less the removal of on-street parking in favor of more space for walking, cycling, street life, and vegetation.

The results of Model 3 in Table 6 indicate sociodemographic attributes that are associated with acceptability of on-street parking removal. Being of older age, living in a household with children, having a higher household income, and having serious health issues or disabilities are associated with lower acceptability. On the contrary, female gender, tertiary education, and living with a partner or spouse are associated with higher acceptability. Among all these relationships, having a health issue or disability stands out as the strongest negative predictor of acceptability, while tertiary education stands out as the strongest positive predictor.

The results of Model 4 (full model) in Table 6 indicate significant factors when all explanatory variables are modeled together. It is again found that those who regularly park on the streets of the city center tend

to have lower acceptability. Moreover, now that additional explanatory variables are accounted for, the purpose of on-street parking yields significant results. Those who park and live in the city center tend to have lower acceptability compared to those who park for other purposes including work-related activities, shopping, and recreation. Car-related attitudinal variables remain significant. Car dependence, preference towards the car as a travel mode, and car ownership are all associated with lower acceptability of on-street parking removal. Moreover, those who intend to use the car less in the future tend to have higher acceptability of the intervention, while those who intend to use it more tend to have lower acceptability. Satisfaction with travel to the city center and satisfaction with travel in the city in general are associated with higher acceptability, while satisfaction with walking in the city center is associated with lower acceptability. Tertiary education and living with a partner or spouse are related to higher acceptability, while age is linked to lower acceptability.

4.5. Acceptability across space

The final analysis aims to identify patterns of acceptability across space. Fig. 6 shows two maps of Copenhagen that include the boundaries of the different districts of the municipality as well as the boundaries of Frederiksberg which is an enclave within the municipality of Copenhagen but represents a distinct municipality. Fig. 6 (left) shows hot spots and cold spots of acceptability across residential locations. It is observed that the city center is a major cold spot of acceptability; in other words, a large cluster of lower acceptability is found in the city center, exactly where on-street parking was about to be removed. Another smaller, and less significant cold spot is observed in the north-eastern part of the city (Østerbro district). Conversely two areas adjacent to the city center are hot spots of acceptability (clusters of high values) (Nørrebro and Vesterbro districts). Moreover, there are other smaller hot spots in areas close to the north-western boundaries of the City of Copenhagen. Fig. 6 (right) shows the results of the hot spot analysis across workplace locations. It is observed that there are considerably fewer hot spots and cold spots across workplace locations than across residential locations. There is a small cold spot in the city center, while there are two somewhat more extensive hot spots in the areas adjacent to the city center towards the north (Nørrebro) and south (Amager).

5. Discussion

5.1. Discussion of the results

The results show that a large majority of the survey participants in Copenhagen supports the removal of on-street parking from the city center and its transformation into space for street life, cycling, and vegetation. This finding is in line with previous findings suggesting that if eliminating on-street parking is combined with a reuse of space for purposes that improve livability or active mobility, public acceptability is likely to be high (Kirschner & Lanzendorf, 2020b; Lanzendorf et al., 2024). This finding is also in line with studies on other transport policies suggesting that a combination of push (restrictions or removal) and pull (improvements in public space, public transport, or active mobility) measures is required for policies to be acceptable (Gärbling & Schuitema, 2007; Lanzendorf et al., 2024; Thaller et al., 2024). Despite wide support for transforming on-street parking in the city center into space for other purposes, there is a considerable minority that views such a policy as negative. The study identifies a range of factors that contribute to a positive or negative evaluation of this policy.

Parking frequency is found to be a key driver of acceptability of parking removal. The more frequently one parks on the streets of the city center the more likely they are to hold negative views of parking removal. Car users who live in the city center and park on the streets of the city center have, on average, the most negative view of the policy, as revealed by statistical as well as spatial analyses. This is in agreement with previous literature showing that on-street parking removal is less supported by car owners who park on the street (Baumgartner & Lanzendorf, 2025). This indicates that even though these residents were offered access to a nearby parking garage without extra cost, on-street parking was still a preferable option for them, probably due to proximity and convenience. Although residents of the city center are found to be the least supportive of the proposed policy, their views might have been even more negative if it was not for the option to use the parking garage, which has been shown to be a positively viewed countermeasure (Baumgartner & Lanzendorf, 2025). Conversely, those who never use on-street parking in the city center find the policy highly acceptable. The latter group represents the majority in Copenhagen, since very few residents (less than 10%) travel regularly to the city center by car and even fewer choose to use on-street parking. Therefore, since most residents do not use on-street parking in the city center, they are supportive of transforming it into space for other uses. Parking behavior can also explain why workplace location is not found to play a key role in acceptability, as shown in the spatial analysis above. Only a

Fig. 6. Hot spots and cold spots of acceptability of on street parking removal across residential locations (left) and across workplace locations (right).

very small portion of residents commute to the city center by car – hence the small cold spot in the city center – and commuting by car typically occurs for workplaces in the periphery. Therefore, the commuting experience of most car users as well as those who use other modes is not directly affected by the reduced parking supply in the city center.

A key factor that shapes the acceptability of on-street parking removal is found to be car dependence. Car ownership, high car dependence, preference towards the car as travel mode, and intentions to use the car more often in the future are all associated with lower acceptability of on-street parking removal. This is in line with previous literature suggesting that car users, car lovers, and particularly those highly dependent on the car are less likely to support car restrictions and post-car transitions in general (Baumgartner & Lanzendorf, 2025; Goetting et al., 2025; Kirschner & Lanzendorf, 2020b; Lanzendorf et al., 2024) due to a high perceived personal cost (de Groot & Schuitema, 2012; Mouratidis, 2025a).

The finding on car dependence linked to lower acceptability may explain why the acceptability of on-street parking removal is higher in areas adjacent to the city center. As the study focuses on residents of the municipality of Copenhagen, the districts adjacent to the city center like Nørrebro and Vesterbro are in close proximity to the city center, and thus central as well as densely populated. Therefore, they offer good accessibility to multiple destinations through public transport and active mobility, resulting in possibly lower car dependence. Moreover, residents of these districts may comfortably travel to the city center by bike, public transport, or even on foot. As a result, most of these residents are not negatively affected by parking changes in the city center. The smaller hot spot of high acceptability towards the northern-western boundary of the municipality Copenhagen might be due to residents of these areas not being so car dependent or not frequently using on-street parking in the city center. These areas are mainly residential and of lower density than the areas adjacent to the city center but are still relatively central if one looks at the Metropolitan Area of Copenhagen and with good provisions in terms of public transport and cycling infrastructure. The cold spot of low acceptability found in the north-eastern part of the city (Østerbro district) could be possibly attributed to sociodemographic factors such as older age and higher income which are associated with lower acceptability. These findings suggest that geography and spatial characteristics influence acceptability, in line with previous relevant studies (Baumgartner & Lanzendorf, 2025; Kyriakidis et al., 2023; Lanzendorf et al., 2024; Tvinnereim et al., 2020), through factors such as travel behavior, car dependence, attitudes, and sociodemographic profile.

Travel satisfaction is another factor found to contribute to the acceptability of on-street parking removal. Satisfaction with traveling to the city center and traveling in the city in general are associated with higher acceptability, while satisfaction with walking in the city center is associated with lower acceptability. These findings could be interpreted considering the local context. Since car-based mobility in Copenhagen is relatively restricted at least in the urban core, those who have positive experiences under these conditions are likely to support additional parking regulations. Moreover, those who perceive that walking in the city center needs improvements, hence reporting low walking satisfaction, are likely to support the conversion of on-street parking to space for walking or other uses. These findings are in accordance with the idea that travel satisfaction may influence travel-related attitudes (De Vos, 2019; Kyriakidis et al., 2023).

Sociodemographic profile is another factor found to shape the acceptability of on-street parking removal. We find that acceptability is lower among older adults, people with health issues or disabilities, households with children, and people with higher income, while it is higher among females, people with tertiary education, and those living with a partner or spouse. These findings suggest that the perceived personal cost (mainly in terms of possible inconvenience or burden) or personal outcome expectations vary across groups of people with different characteristics. People with serious health issues or disabilities

are likely to be more car dependent (Appendix C) so they might feel that eliminating on-street parking reduces their mobility, as previously discussed in Mouratidis (2025a), even though parking spaces reserved for people with disabilities were not affected by the policy. Females are less car dependent on average (Appendix C), so this might make them more supportive of parking removal in favor of active travel modes. This finding is in accordance with a relevant study in Germany (Goetting et al., 2025) but contrasts a study where females were found to be less supportive of an intervention restricting car use in Athens, Greece (Kyriakidis et al., 2023). Finally, those with tertiary education are more supportive of car-free lifestyles or generally transport policies towards environmental sustainability, as also shown by previous research (Goetting et al., 2025; Mehdizadeh et al., 2024; Mouratidis & Næss, 2024).

5.2. Limitations and future research

The study is characterized by certain limitations. First, the results apply to the specific context of Copenhagen. Local socioeconomic and political conditions, culture and attitudes, climate, and topography may contribute to the relationships identified in the analysis. Therefore, investigating this topic in other cities is recommended. Second, the results apply only to on-street parking in the city center. We cannot assume that results would be similar in other areas, for example neighborhood centers or residential streets. Analyzing policies in such areas would be an important supplement to the current findings. Third, our analysis focuses on acceptability prior to the implementation of the parking policy. As shown in previous studies, public support for transport policies often grows after implementation. Future studies could replicate this study after implementation and compare contributing factors of public acceptability. Fourth, participation in the study was voluntary and therefore, only a part of the citizen panel completed the survey. Moreover, the response rate from the street survey could not be estimated. The results might suffer from non-response bias. For example, residents who are more or less supportive of the Municipality's plan than the average in the population might be more eager to participate in the survey and thus overrepresented in the final sample. Similarly, respondents in the street survey may not be completely representative of the car users of the city center. Fifth, the final sample consists of respondents from both survey distribution methods. This was done to increase the representation of car users of the city center and help increase variability for the analysis of factors contributing to acceptability. However, it should be again acknowledged that the final sample is not fully representative of the population. Therefore, acceptability might differ between the sample and the population. In particular, since the users of on-street parking in the city center have been intentionally oversampled, the overall acceptability in the population might be higher than the one reported in the study. We have attempted to address the issue of representativeness by including a series of behavioral, attitudinal, spatial, and sociodemographic variables in ordinal regression modeling. Sixth, although the study includes spatial analysis that shows spatial patterns of acceptability, with significant findings mainly for residential locations, specific spatial characteristics like local population density and accessibility to public transport have not been analyzed here. A future analysis of detailed spatial characteristics could therefore be part of a follow-up study. Moreover, geospatial modeling with non-stationary approaches like multiscale geographically weighted regression could meaningfully extend the present analysis.

6. Conclusions

In this paper, we have investigated public acceptability of removing on-street parking and transforming it into space for street life, cycling, and vegetation, based on a real case example from the city center of Copenhagen. A large majority of Copenhagen residents who participated in the study are positive about the intervention, while there is a

considerable minority that holds negative views.

Several factors contributing to the acceptability of removing on-street parking have been identified. *Parking frequency* is a key factor. The more one uses on-street parking, the less likely they are to be supportive of removing it. Residents of the local area who permanently park on the street are likely to be against removing the parking spaces they are currently using, even if access to a nearby parking garage is offered without additional costs. *Car-based mobility* and *pro-car attitudes* also result in lower acceptability. Car ownership, preference for car use, intentions to increase car use, and, most of all, high car dependence are associated with lower acceptability. *Residential location* also relates to acceptability, with clusters of lower acceptability found in the area of intervention, and high clusters found in adjacent areas characterized by low car dependence and proximity to the city center. *Travel satisfaction* is also linked to acceptability. Those that are less satisfied with traveling to the city center and within the city in general are likely to be less supportive of on-street parking removal. In terms of *sociodemographic attributes*, older age, serious health issues or disabilities, living with children, and higher income are all associated with lower acceptability, while female gender, tertiary education, and living with a partner or spouse are associated with higher acceptability.

The study's findings have important implications for urban and transport policy. *First*, the overall high acceptability of transforming on-street parking into space for alternative uses supports the idea that a combination of push (restrictions) and pull (livability and active mobility) measures makes post-car transitions more acceptable. Therefore, plans that restrict parking supply should be combined with attractive plans for reuse of space as much as possible. Communicating the reuse of space and its livability benefits in public deliberation, co-creation activities, and pilot trials are key for increasing public acceptability. *Second*, an important implication is that to increase the popularity of such policies, overall strategies that help decrease car dependence and pro-car attitudes should be in place. Parking restrictions and reduced parking supply should be preceded by other measures that reduce car dependence and change attitudes such as campaigns to improve public awareness, compact city policies, and improvements regarding public transport and active mobility. *Third*, it is shown that even in a city where car dependence is generally lower compared to most cities around the globe, reducing on-street parking supply is not acceptable by everyone. Policies have personal costs – such as reduced convenience, increased travel time, financial burden, or reduced mobility – that may disproportionately affect certain residents, and especially those directly affected by them. While it is highly unlikely that parking regulations are completely beneficial to everyone, local authorities could aim to reduce personal costs for residents of the local area, vulnerable groups such as people with disabilities, and car-dependent individuals who have no alternative to car-based transport. Co-creation activities and pilot trials targeting such groups ahead of problem definition, design, and implementation can provide alternative solutions and a sense of co-ownership to those most affected by restrictive measures. Eventually, some compromise is usually needed, from both sides, to balance positive societal impacts and negative personal costs for certain individuals. *Finally*, it should be noted that although acceptability is lower among certain people, the actual impact of the policy on the population should be assessed after its implementation.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Kostas Mouratidis: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization, Data curation. **Hans Skov-Petersen:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Methodology. **Trine Agervig Carstensen:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

The study is part of the research project ELABORATOR (project 101103772) funded by the Horizon Europe program of the European Union. We are grateful to Maria Risom Laursen and the City of Copenhagen for the collaboration throughout this research. We would also like to thank all the participants in the surveys conducted as part of this study.

Appendix

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2026.106836>.

Data availability

The data that has been used is confidential.

References

- Ajzen, I. (2002). Perceived behavioral control, self-efficacy, locus of control, and the theory of planned behavior. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 32(4), 665–683. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1559-1816.2002.tb00236.x>
- Alexandre, B., Reynaud, E., Osiurak, F., & Navarro, J. (2018). Acceptance and acceptability criteria: A literature review. *Cognition, Technology & Work*, 20(2), 165–177. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10111-018-0459-1>
- Banister, D. (2008). The sustainable mobility paradigm. *Transport Policy*, 15(2), 73–80. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tranpol.2007.10.005>
- Baumgartner, A., & Lanzendorf, M. (2025). Where are parking policies most popular? Empirical findings about the influence of the residential neighbourhood and car parking characteristics on public acceptability. *Transport Policy*, 168, 263–278. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tranpol.2025.04.006>
- Börjesson, M., Eliasson, J., Hugosson, M. B., & Brundell-Freij, K. (2012). The Stockholm congestion charges—5 years on. Effects, acceptability and lessons learnt. *Transport Policy*, 20, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tranpol.2011.11.001>
- Burchell, J., Ison, S., Enoch, M., & Budd, L. (2019). Implementation of the workplace parking levy as a transport policy instrument. *Journal of Transport Geography*, 80, Article 102543. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2019.102543>
- City Council of Seville. (2021). *Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan 2030 (PMUS)*. Seville: Ayuntamiento de Sevilla.
- City of Amsterdam. (2013). *Mobility Plan for Amsterdam in 2030*. Amsterdam: Gemeente Amsterdam.
- City of Copenhagen. (2022). *Urban space and traffic plan for the medieval city*. Copenhagen: Københavns Kommune.
- City of Paris. (2023). *Climate Plan 2024–2030*. Paris: Ville de Paris.
- Creutzig, F., Javadi, A., Soomauroo, Z., Lohrey, S., Milojevic-Dupont, N., Ramakrishnan, A., ... Zausch, J. M. (2020). Fair street space allocation: ethical principles and empirical insights. *Transport Reviews*, 40(6), 711–733. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01441647.2020.1762795>
- de Groot, J. I. M., & Schuitema, G. (2012). How to make the unpopular popular? Policy characteristics, social norms and the acceptability of environmental policies. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 19–20, 100–107. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2012.03.004>
- De Vos, J. (2019). Satisfaction-induced travel behaviour. *Transportation Research Part F: Traffic Psychology and Behaviour*, 63, 12–21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trf.2019.03.001>
- European Commission. (2019). *2018 Road safety statistics: what is behind the figures?* Brussels: European Commission.
- Gärling, T., & Schuitema, G. (2007). Travel demand management targeting reduced private car use: Effectiveness, public acceptability and political feasibility. *Journal of Social Issues*, 63(1), 139–153.
- Gillen, D. W. (1978). Parking policy, parking location decisions and the distribution of congestion. *Transportation*, 7(1), 69–85. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00148372>
- Glavic, D., Mladenovic, M., Luttinen, T., Cicevic, S., & Trifunovic, A. (2017). Road to price: User perspectives on road pricing in transition country. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 105, 79–94. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tra.2017.08.016>
- Goetting, K., Liebe, U., & Becker, S. (2025). From parking place to public space: A factorial survey experiment on public acceptability of parking space reallocation in Germany. *Climate Policy*, 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14693062.2025.2539140>
- Graham-Rowe, E., Skippon, S., Gardner, B., & Abraham, C. (2011). Can we reduce car use and, if so, how? A review of available evidence. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 45(5), 401–418. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tra.2011.02.001>

- Hoffmann, B. (2019). Air pollution in cities: Urban and transport planning determinants and health in cities. In M. Nieuwenhuijsen, & H. Khreis (Eds.), *Integrating human health into urban and transport planning: A framework* (pp. 425–441). Cham, Switzerland: Springer.
- IPCC. (2023). *Climate Change 2023: Synthesis report*. Geneva: IPCC.
- Kirschner, F., & Lanzendorf, M. (2020a). Parking management for promoting sustainable transport in urban neighbourhoods. A review of existing policies and challenges from a German perspective. *Transport Reviews*, 40(1), 54–75. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01441647.2019.1666929>
- Kirschner, F., & Lanzendorf, M. (2020b). Support for innovative on-street parking policies: Empirical evidence from an urban neighborhood. *Journal of Transport Geography*, 85, Article 102726. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2020.102726>
- Kroesen, M., Handy, S., & Chorus, C. (2017). Do attitudes cause behavior or vice versa? An alternative conceptualization of the attitude-behavior relationship in travel behavior modeling. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 101, 190–202. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tra.2017.05.013>
- Kuss, P., & Nicholas, K. A. (2022). A dozen effective interventions to reduce car use in European cities: Lessons learned from a meta-analysis and transition management. *Case Studies on Transport Policy*, 10(3), 1494–1513. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cstp.2022.02.001>
- Kyriakidis, C., Chatziioannou, I., Iliadis, F., Nikitas, A., & Bakogiannis, E. (2023). Evaluating the public acceptance of sustainable mobility interventions responding to Covid-19: The case of the Great Walk of Athens and the importance of citizen engagement. *Cities*, 132, Article 103966. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2022.103966>
- Lanzendorf, M., Baumgartner, A., & Klüner, N. (2024). Do citizens support the transformation of urban transport? Evidence for the acceptability of parking management, car lane conversion and road closures from a German case study. *Transportation*, 51(6), 2073–2101. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11116-023-10398-w>
- Leroutier, M., & Quirion, P. (2023). Tackling car emissions in urban areas: Shift, avoid, improve. *Ecological Economics*, 213, Article 107951. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2023.107951>
- Lightner, J. S., Vonnahme, G., Chesnut, S., Ziegler, N., Nguyen, N., Sylvaine, C., ... Grimes, A. (2025). Funding for public transportation: results from a Midwest exit poll. *Transportation Research Interdisciplinary Perspectives*, 31, Article 101433. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trip.2025.101433>
- Litman, T. (2017). *Parking management best practices*. Oxon: Routledge.
- Mehdizadeh, M., Solbu, G., Klöckner, C. A., & Moe Skjølsvold, T. (2024). Navigating acceptance and controversy of transport policies. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 187, Article 104176. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tra.2024.104176>
- Milenković, M., Glavić, D., & Maričić, M. (2019). Determining factors affecting congestion pricing acceptability. *Transport Policy*, 82, 58–74. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tranpol.2019.08.004>
- Mingardo, G., van Wee, B., & Rye, T. (2015). Urban parking policy in Europe: A conceptualization of past and possible future trends. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 74, 268–281. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tra.2015.02.005>
- Moeinaddini, A., & Habibian, M. (2023). Transportation demand management policy efficiency: An attempt to address the effectiveness and acceptability of policy packages. *Transport Policy*, 141, 317–330. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tranpol.2023.07.027>
- Morris, E. A., Blumenberg, E., & Guerra, E. (2020). Does lacking a car put the brakes on activity participation? Private vehicle access and access to opportunities among low-income adults. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 136, 375–397. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tra.2020.03.021>
- Mouratidis, K. (2021). Urban planning and quality of life: A review of pathways linking the built environment to subjective well-being. *Cities*, 115, Article 103229. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2021.103229>
- Mouratidis, K. (2025a). Reducing car dependence: Benefits, strategies, unintended consequences, and future directions of post-car urban transitions. *Planning Practice and Research*, 40(4), 889–910. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02697459.2025.2507325>
- Mouratidis, K. (2025b). Transport and quality of life: The car and its link to subjective well-being, health, and life domains. *Transport Policy*, 168, 101–111. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tranpol.2025.04.014>
- Mouratidis, K., & Næss, P. (2024). Climate change concern as driver of sustainable mobility and reduced car use. *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, 134, Article 104345. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2024.104345>
- Næss, P. (2020). Sustainable mobility. In O. B. Jensen, C. Lassen, V. Kaufmann, M. Freudendal-Pedersen, & I. S. G. Lange (Eds.), *Handbook of urban mobilities* (pp. 398–408). Oxon: Routledge.
- Næss, P. (2025). Four common misconceptions in quantitative studies of the built environment and travel. *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, 139, Article 104597. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2025.104597>
- Nielsen, T. A. S., & Skov-Petersen, H. (2018). Bikeability – Urban structures supporting cycling. Effects of local, urban and regional scale urban form factors on cycling from home and workplace locations in Denmark. *Journal of Transport Geography*, 69, 36–44. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2018.04.015>
- Okraszewska, R., Romanowska, A., Clarissa Laetsch, D., Gobis, A., Reisch, L. A., Kamphuis, C. B. M., ... Żukowska, J. (2024). Interventions reducing car usage: Systematic review and meta-analysis. *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, 131, Article 104217. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2024.104217>
- Oslo Municipality. (2019). *The Car-Free Liveability Programme 2019*. Oslo: Oslo Kommune.
- Santos, G., Behrendt, H., & Teytelboym, A. (2010). Part II: Policy instruments for sustainable road transport. *Research in Transportation Economics*, 28(1), 46–91. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.retrec.2010.03.002>
- Scheepers, C. E., Wendel-Vos, G. C. W., den Broeder, J. M., van Kempen, E. E. M. M., van Wesemael, P. J. V., & Schuit, A. J. (2014). Shifting from car to active transport: A systematic review and meta-analysis of interventions. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 70, 264–280. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tra.2014.10.015>
- Schmaus, A., Creutzig, F., Koch, N., Nachtigall, F., & Molkenhain, N. (2025). An urban shared pooled mobility system cuts distance travelled by over 50%. *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, 144, Article 104726. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2025.104726>
- Schuitema, G., Steg, L., & Forward, S. (2010). Explaining differences in acceptability before and acceptance after the implementation of a congestion charge in Stockholm. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 44(2), 99–109. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tra.2009.11.005>
- Schuitema, G., Steg, L., & Rothengatter, J. A. (2010). The acceptability, personal outcome expectations, and expected effects of transport pricing policies. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 30(4), 587–593. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2010.05.002>
- Semenescu, A., Gavreliuc, A., & Sărbescu, P. (2020). 30 Years of soft interventions to reduce car use – A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, 85, Article 102397. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2020.102397>
- Sheller, M. (2018). *Mobility justice: The politics of movement in an age of extremes*. London: Verso Books.
- Shoup, D. (2021). *The high cost of free parking*. Oxfordshire: Routledge.
- Stefánsdóttir, H., Mouratidis, K., Rynning, M. K., & Meyer, S. F. (2024). Perceived walkability and daily walking behaviour in a “small city context” – The case of Norway. *Journal of Transport Geography*, 121, Article 104014. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2024.104014>
- Steg, L. (2003). Factors influencing the acceptability and effectiveness of transport pricing. In J. Schade, & B. Schlag (Eds.), *Acceptability of transport pricing strategies* (pp. 187–202). Oxford: Elsevier Science.
- Sun, X., Feng, S., & Lu, J. (2016). Psychological factors influencing the public acceptability of congestion pricing in China. *Transportation Research Part F: Traffic Psychology and Behaviour*, 41, 104–112. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trf.2016.06.015>
- Thaller, A., Michael, W., Eva, F., Raphaela, M., & Posch, A. (2024). Pushing low-carbon mobility: A survey experiment on the public acceptance of disruptive policy packages. *Climate Policy*, 24(7), 949–962. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14693062.2024.2302322>
- Thøgersen, J., Vatn, A., Aasen, M., Dunlap, R. E., Fisher, D. R., Hellevik, O., & Stern, P. (2021). Why do people continue driving conventional cars despite climate change? Social-psychological and institutional insights from a survey of Norwegian commuters. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 79, Article 102168. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2021.102168>
- Tvinnereim, E., Haarstad, H., Rødeseike, A., & Bugnion, V. (2020). Explaining public acceptance of congestion charging: The role of geographical variation in the Bergen case. *Case Studies on Transport Policy*, 8(3), 992–1001. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cstp.2020.04.007>
- van Wee, B., Annema, J. A., & van Barneveld, S. (2023). Controversial policies: Growing support after implementation. A discussion paper. *Transport Policy*, 139, 79–86. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tranpol.2023.05.010>
- van Wee, B., De Vos, J., & Maat, K. (2019). Impacts of the built environment and travel behaviour on attitudes: Theories underpinning the reverse causality hypothesis. *Journal of Transport Geography*, 80, Article 102540. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2019.102540>